

Identify and Ranking the Factors Influencing Insurance Company's Competitive Advantage with Qualitative and Quantitative Methods

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Abstract

This research has been performed to identify the factors that can help to attain competitive advantage in insurance companies. In addition, in order to determine which factors have more priorities to attain by insurance companies, their ranking also been considered. The research way is exploratory mixed method. First, the factors affecting on attain competitive advantage of insurance have been identified through selecting the factors that were most frequent, this factors were ranked with fuzzy AHP technique using paired comparisons questionnaire. In order to do an interview, by using the purposive sampling, 17 experts and top managers of insurance were selected as a sample and also then these people responded to paired comparisons questionnaire. Identified factors were divided to six criteria including comfort, quality, customer responsiveness, creativity, services and brands. The research results showed that among comfort and welfare criteria, the number of representatives with fuzzy weight 0/2722 is in first priorities and the flexibility in presenting insurance services based on the conditions of policyholders with 0/2004 weight have second priority. Among services qualitative criteria, the way of communication of employee of insurance company with 0/2173 weight is in first place. Also, for ranking and identifying the fuzzy weights, the indices of respond to customers, innovation, internet service and brand was done.

Keywords: *Competitive Advantages Mixed Procedure, Fuzzy Hierarchy Analysis, Insurance Companies.*

1. Introduction

During the past 20 years and coinciding with appear new markets, the economy of developed countries, in terms of type and nature of work and place and how to make surplus value, is faced with revolution. Key factor of this revolution is nothing except the significant growth of service unit. This unit's growth caused fundamental changes in work methods and production nature and process and created value. As a result of this changes, there were marked change in valuable references of new organizations. In service industries, process and nature of business rather than visible resources and manufacturing facilities, to create a value, is depended to invisible resources and capitals (Azizi & et.al, 2012).

Abbasi and Salehi (2011) also argue that service organizations are important factors to attain sustainable competitive advantage, competent and service - oriented staffs (human resources). This procedure for valuable and impalpable resources reflects that there is a fundamental change in nature of competitive advantage. Almost all of this intangible assets are managed and directed by human talent.

The issue of compete in all industries and services have some common points, in quite competitive markets, the company is successful that have significant profit through reduce the costs, on one hand, and promote the production qualitative and delivery the services on other hand. But in insurance, unlike industries, the sold product is not tangible and also majority of policyholders do not benefit from this services except having peace of mind and relief, because they don't face with any damages. While other industries in addition to selling a physical product have some services during using the product, all the sellers can judge about company's products quality and how to service delivery. So competition in insurance is more complex and have more delicacy. Privatization and its subsequent release were most important events in insurance industry in recent years that changed industry very much and has provided the advanced field

of competition. In addition to two issues of privatization and release, news of entry of foreign (external) insurances to country is another issue that necessitate improvement of competitive environment and company's focus on attaining benefits superior to competitors (Mazloomi & Dadvand,2012).

In current environment of the insurance industry, companies that identify their distinct competencies and preserve them compared to their internal and external competitors , are able to increase productivity and reduce risk, so the key issue is how can create higher profitability than competitors in an insurance company and on other hand how can lowered company's risk at same time? Recognizing competitive advantage and its factors to achieve this, provide some respond areas to this problems. Therefore, according to these, the aim of this study is identify and ranking affecting factors on attain competitive advantage in insurance companies of Bandar Abbas city.

2. Literatures

Researchers are considered insurance industry as an important factor in development of counties; because insurance have a significant role in growth of different economic sectors and increase investment incentives through covering damages caused by economic activities and community development. The insurance activities in Iran were started since 1931 Hijri by foreign companies, subsequently the activity of first domestic insurance company, as Iran Insurance Company, has begun in 1935 Hijri. During this period the insurance industry has seen many ups and downs such as: establish different insurance companies and subsequent establish Central Insurance in 1971, and then approve the law of establishing the private insurance institutions in 2001 and at last, the decision to transfer state insurance companies (except Iran Insurance) , in order to implement article 44 of the Constitution. Being a state owned companies and lack of private sector activities in insurance market during the last decades, actually caused to a monopoly and therefore ineffective of activities of this industry.

By Implementing release policies, deregulation and privatization, the insurance industry of country have started its upward trend. This has resulted to create a competitive atmosphere between insurance companies and subsequently development of this industry. In the past in many areas, customers had to us exclusive services and products with any quality and any delivery method, but now according to Article 44 of Constitution and policies of delegations and entry of private sector, in many of business sectors and As well as insurance industry, product exhibiter and service providers should have intense competition to attract customers. They are faced with powerful customers and if they are not able to meet their requests, they must leave the competition. Therefore, companies that are counter with powerful customers should turn to new ways in business, in order to increase their influence on customer. On the other hand, tariff system in some services of insurance market cause to foreclose the freedom of insurance companies in determining the rate. So, in such market, competition between insurance companies is in the field of methods, offer new services and customer orientation, so that facilitate, accelerate and improve delivery of services. Today, the change speed is such that previous models and theories are rapidly changing and experts offer new methods and techniques every day (Sepahvand, 2016).

3. Competitive Advantage

The concept of competition and competitive advantage are from the economic concepts that can seek its history in the theory of Absolute Advantage by Adam Smith and the theory of Comparative advantage by Ricardo. Competitive advantage is the company's ability to attract customers than competitors, with focused on organizational abilities and capacities (Burney, 1991).

To better understanding of the subject, first it is necessary to present the definition and its concept. Obviously, more comprehensive definition result to better understanding of matter. In this regard, some of definitions by experts about competitive advantage are as follow:

“Competitive advantage is to increase attractiveness of company suggestions compared to competitors based on customers' points of view” (j. Kigan, 2011).

“Competitive advantage is presentable values of company for customers, so that this values are higher than customer's costs” (Porter, 1980).

The concept of competitive advantage have a direct relation with values of customers so that in a comparative spectrum whatever

values introduced by a company be closer to customers values or be more coincide with them , it can be said that company have more advantages in one or more criteria of competition, compared to its competitors(Mehri and Hosseini, 2005).

Competitive advantage include a set of factors or abilities that always enable the company to show better performance than competitors (Sadri, 2001).

Investigating the offered definitions by experts about competitive advantage (Burney, 2006) showed that the main emphasis of competitive advantage is on having superior in one or more factors of customers compared to their competitors. Towards creating competitive advantage two points are important: first, this path is a continuous process that lead to an excellent performance and competitiveness of company; i. e. if the company through its competencies is able to create stable competitive advantage that is valuable for customers and be always superior than competitors, in fact leave an competent performance and lead to competitiveness. Second, due to increased environmental complexities and intensity of competition, competitive advantage is easily imitate by competitors or according to customers points of view will fade away soon and should be replace with new advantages. Accordingly, company should think about finding a stable competitive advantage (Attaran and et .al. 2012).

To create and maintain stability of competitive advantage, the competences are necessary that according to company's abilities make value for customers. The company's references include types of assets, capabilities, organizational processes, information, knowledge and etc., and company control them so that develop and implement valuable strategies. This references can be categorize in tangible, intangible and organizational clusters.

The capabilities of company, is a mixed of skills, knowledge and behaviors that exist in overtime and reflects in people, systems, processes and structures. In other word, company used skills to convert data to outputs, in order to use of mixed tangible and intangible resources in the form of organizational processes for achieve objectives such as: customer service, superior product development capabilities, innovativeness of services and products. Competencies are considered as a complete combination of assets, resources and processes that allow company to respond to customer needs. Those competencies have strategic value that cab create value for customers. As said before, the main company's objective of creating a competitive advantage according to its resources and capabilities, is to make competitiveness and attain to a privileged position in terms of performance in customer - based markets. The key of this problem, i. e. achieve to competitiveness, is stabling competitive advantages based on knowledge principle and understanding the customer needs and focus on customer as well as develop processes from customer points of view. Stable competitive advantage are those advantages that are valuable for customers by taking advantage of the competence of the organization, not being easily imitated by competitors , and brought good performance and competitiveness for company.

The concept of competitive advantage indicated the superiority from certain capabilities or combining of abilities that the superior solely or largely have than its competitors. The most important properties of competitive advantage are its strength, invulnerability and value.

4. Experimental History

The results of research by Aghazade and et. al. (2015) as "investigating the innovate strategies in insurance industry of country with blue ocean approach" showed that online services dimensions, physical evidences and creativity are at inappropriate level of function and active companies in insurance industry in all dimensions, except physical evidences , have similar performance. In follow, the way to achieve the blue ocean of insurance industry, in form of four measures and for actions (create, increase, decrease and elimination) is shown.

The results of study by Hosseini and Shams (2014) as "the impact of positive organizational behavior and open innovation on improve competitive advantage" indicate confirming the positive impact of positive organizational behavior and open innovation on improve competitive advantage and first and second hypothesis concerning the impact of positive organizational behavior in open innovation and the effect of positive organizational behavior on competitive advantage are confirmed but third hypothesis concerning the impact of open innovation on competitive advantage is nor confirmed.

The results of study by Sehat & et.al (2015) about the relation between organizational innovation and competitive advantage in

insurance companies show that there is a positive and meaningful relation between organizational innovation in whole and types of this with competitive advantage in insurance companies and between types of innovation, innovation in product have more relation with competitive advantage in insurance companies. Also, the results of single sample t-test show that insurance companies are in good conditions just in terms of process innovation.

The results of data analysis of the study by Bagheri et.al. (2014) as “investigating the effect of tendency of managers to market on gain competitive advantage in terms of competitive intelligence dimensions and organizational factors that are done by structural equation modeling and by using LISREL software” indicated that increased level of marketing of managers ,despite mediator of intelligence lead to attain and maintain the competitive advantage of companies. At that time, the study results show that the variables related to organizational factors have no significant and direct efficacy on competitive advantage.

Khef Elahi et.al (2009) have investigated and study with title how strategic management of human resources leads to improvement of organizational performance through attain competitive advantage and market oriented? The results indicated that use of human resource as a competitive advantage means analyzing the factors that are necessary for long time success of organization.

Mehri and Khodada Hosseini (2005) performed a study as “designing the competitive advantages for automotive industry of Iran that according to theatrical fundamentals of strategic management of marketing “, expressed three sets of attitudes, in relation to competitive advantage. First attitude is resources and organizational capabilities, second attitude is resources and environment capabilities and third attitude is resources and inter organizational relations and its synergy as a reference of competitive advantage. The results showed that the factors affecting on competitive advantage, according to importance and impact rate, are competitive intelligence, organizational capabilities, environmental capabilities and connectivity capabilities, respectively.

Rezaei Dolatabadi et.al. (2011) in a study as “evaluation of the effect of competitive intelligence on creating competitive advantage”, present a suggestive model for exiting companies in Isfahan’s science and technology town. This research ‘s results indicated that using of a competitive intelligence program cause to achieve a competitive advantage compared to competitors and ensure survival of the organization.

Veravardena and Arven (2004) presented a study as “investigate the market – oriented companies and histories of stable competitive advantage”. This study is a research findings that refers to study the role of learning capacity focused on marketing and marketing capabilities in competitive strategy based on innovation in stable competitive advantage. Findings show that entrepreneurship is an important factor of stable competitive advantage (SCA), while learning capability focused on market leads to higher levels of innovation and marketing capability provides stable competitive advantage.

Mocha’s findings (2012) as “main competencies and competitive advantage in Kenya’s insurance companies” showed that although insurance companies consider different areas as their competencies, there is a meaningful relation between main competencies and competitive advantage. This study also showed that core competencies have a significant impact on competitive advantage. So, insurance companies should maintain their main competencies to attain those competitive advantage that are considered as success.

Optemihen (2011) in a research as “attain competitive advantage in insurance industry (the effect of marketing innovation and creativity)” concluded that creativity and innovation in marketing is essential in organizational success. Also he concluded that insurance industry can improve its business through innovation and creativity and achieve to a stable competitive advantage.

The study by Jannat et. al. (2015) as “investigate effective factors on effective competitive advantage between supermarkets in Kenya” showed that product innovation, information technology. Manager’s aspects and relations with providers have direct and positive effect on competitive advantage of supermarkets.

The study findings of Ecnego (2016) as “evaluation of effective factors on banks competitive advantage in Kenya” showed that banks managing should present more efficiency quality services and more affordable and attractive rates, investment in IT platforms as well as employ effective and efficient human resources to achieve competitive advantage.

Sheykh (2015) in a research as “investigating the effective factors on competitive advantage of educational services in Jordan’s universities “concluded that there is a meaningful relation between effective factors on marketing competitive advantage of

educational services. This differences are resulted from factors such as age, education, expertise, nationality and payment methods of student.

5. Materials & Methods

The way that is used in this study is combined method type exploratory. The combine's research method (Tashaakori& teddli. 2003) is a procedure to collecting and analyzing the qualitative and quantitative data in a study or a set of studies, based on primacy and sequence of information (Cresweel, 2003).

In this study, qualitative data are considered very important and in data collection sequence, first qualitative and the quantitative data are collected (Bazargan, 2009). In facts, researcher at first collect qualitative data to detect the condition of a phenomenon and then by collecting quantitative information specify the relations that are from findings of qualitative data.

5.1 Data Collecting Tools

In this study, the data collecting tools include semi – structural interviews and a paired comparisons questionnaire.

In semi – structural interview, the questions are not fully open or fully closed, but also according to the structural rate of questions, participants are guide toward desirable respond. At the beginning of the interview, a brief explanation about the topic, aims and method of research are presented and in order to avoid bias in responds, they are guided according to the necessity of responds. The interview's questions have been developed based on literature and the opinion of experts and professionals.

After that the effecting factors on insurance competitive advantage were identified by using interview with experts and managers, the factors that have higher frequency, are selected and then through a fuzzy hierarchical analysis technique (FAHP) and were ranked by using a paired comparison questionnaire. This questionnaire include 6 paired comparison matrixes. Also, to evaluate the reliability, retest reliability is used.

5.2 Validity and Reliability of Research

In order to ensure the validity and reliability of interview, first, the validity of questions is examined by experts and the structure of questions is revised; the questions were performed on a group of sample members, then to ensure the reliability of questions, after two weeks, again the same questions were asked.

To examine the reliability of paired comparison questionnaire , the geometric mean of all the decision matrixes related to 17 decision makers was earned and to acquire the rate of inconsistency, they were transform to a combined matrix. The rate of inconsistency for combined matrix of measure of comfort ,0.0444; for combined matrix ,0.0362; for combined matrix, 0.0492; for combined matrix, 0.0274; for combined matrix, 0.0162 and for combined matrix, 0.0162 were earned and thus because the inconsistency rate for all combined matrix are between 0.0 to 0.1, the reliability of research questionnaire is also proven.

5.3 Population and Statistical Sample

In recent study, the statistical community include industry experts (professors and scholars in insurance) that in first stage, were interviewed to identify the factors and in second stage, to prioritize the identified factors in previous stage, we taken advantage of their views.

Given that the sample size is not specified before in qualitative research and the sampling process is continue as long as no sufficient dada is achieved, so the nature of repetitive sampling is observed in this study. In fact, when the researcher concluded that by more interviews, no more new data is collected and data saturation is achieved, stop the interview, therefore in this study, to determine sample size for conducting interview and collecting qualitative data, we acted based on expert's opinion and sample size is considered equal to 17. In next step, they were asked to respond paired comparison questionnaire.

The age mean of participants is 28 and above. Also 10 participants were male and 7 of them were women. Most of the participants in this study has bachelor's degree that their number is 12 and 5 participants has master's degree. All of the participants have over 5 years work experience.

5.4 Data Analyzing Methods

The main part of data of the present study is based on qualitative data from interviews. A content analysis of data from interview is possible in 4 ways. In some of this ways, like pseudo – statistical procedure, content analysis of interview is done quantitative, and in some other ways such as code name procedure, editing procedure, and transparency method, qualitative analysis is performed. In recent study, in order to analysis the qualitative data from interview, qualitative data analysis as well as editing method are used. To analysis the quantitative data from paired comparison questionnaire, fuzzy hierarchical analysis technique (FAHP) is used.

5.4.1 Fuzzy Hierarchical Analysis Technique (FAHP)

The analysis of development for fuzzy AHP is presented in 1996 by a Chinese researcher name Young Chang. Because of simple calculations, this method has been used in many cases. The numbers used in this method are fuzzy triangular numbers. According to Chang, by considering any objective, the development analysis can be done for each of goals (g_i). Therefore, there is m developmental analysis for any objective:

$$M_{g_i}^1, M_{g_i}^2, \dots, M_{g_i}^m, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, n$$

Where all $M_{g_i}^j$ are fuzzy triangular numbers. Chang stages of development analysis is as follow:

Stage 1: to obtain a fuzzy composite expansion for any purpose.

If $M_{g_i}^1, M_{g_i}^2, \dots, M_{g_i}^m$ is i^{th} development analysis number for M goal, then expansion fuzzy composite of M goal for i^{th} goal is defined as follow:

$$S_i = \sum_{j=1}^m M_{g_i}^j \otimes \left[\sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m M_{g_i}^j \right]^{-1}$$

Stage 2: to calculate the degree of priority possibility degree) S_i over S_k .

If $S_i = (l_i, m_i, u_i)$ and $S_k = (l_k, m_k, u_k)$, then the priority degree of S_i over S_k that is presented as $V(S_i \geq S_k)$, is defined as follow:

$$V(S_i \geq S_k) = \max_{x \geq y} (\min\{\alpha_{S_i}(x), \alpha_{S_k}(y)\})$$

Where for fuzzy triangular numbers is equal to below equation:

$$V(S_i \geq S_k) = \alpha_{S_i}(d) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{If } (m_i \geq m_k) \\ 0 & \text{If } (l_k \geq u_i) \\ \frac{l_k - u_i}{(m_i - u_i) - (m_k - l_k)} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad \text{Relation 3}$$

In this relation, d corresponding to greater point of intersection between α_{S_i} and α_{S_k} that is shown in (Figure 1):

Figure 1: greater point of intersection between α_{s_i} and α_{s_k}

Stage 3: the priority degree (possibility degree) is a convex fuzzy number S that is greater than the number of convex fuzzy number K, is defined as follow:

$$V(S \geq S_1, S_2, \dots, S_k) = V((S \geq S_1), (S \geq S_2), \dots, (S \geq S_k)) = \min(V((S \geq S_1), (S \geq S_2), \dots, (S \geq S_k))) = \min V(S \geq S_i) , i = 1, 2, \dots, k$$

Relation 4

If for any $k = 1, 2, \dots, n$, $k \neq i$, assume that $d'(A_i) = \min V(S_i \geq S_k)$ then weight vector can be obtained as follow:

$$W' = (d'(A_1), d'(A_2), \dots, d'(A_n))$$

Stage 4: to normalize W' vector and obtain normal vector W.

By using below relation, W' is normalized and become W vector:

$$W_i = \frac{W'_i}{\sum W'_i} \qquad W = (d(A_1), d(A_2), \dots)$$

6. Research Findings

The interview's texts are coded after entering to MAXQDA software. In few parts, to data analysis, Excel and MATLAB software are used.

Generally, factors are divided to 6 classes: standards of comfort, quality, customer responsiveness, creativity, internet services and brand. Their frequency and codes are shown in below.

6.1 Welfare Criteria

This factors included 52 frequencies and 4 codes. This means that participants 52 times refer to different codes. The frequencies of codes have been shown in (Table1).

Rank	Code	Frequency
1	Availability of agencies	15
2	Number of agencies	14
3	Insurance agents' working hours	12
4	Flexibility's rate in offering insurance services according to policy holders condition	11

Table 1: Codes of Comfort and Frequency

6.2 Quality Criteria

This factors include 31 frequencies and 6 codes. This means that participants 31 times refer to 6 different codes in this class. The frequencies of codes are presented in (Table2).

Rank	Factor	Frequency
1	The way of contact of insurance company's staffs	10
2	The rate of presenting free counseling services to policyholders	9
3	Accuracy in doing operation in providing insurance services	5
4	The decor and interior amenities of insurance agency	3
5	The exterior decor and space of insurance agency	2
6	Apparent appearance of staffs in insurance agency	2

Table 2: Codes of Qualities of Services and Frequencies

6.3 Customer Responsiveness Criteria

This factors include 48 frequencies and 4 codes. This means that participants 48 times refer to 4 different codes in this class. The frequencies of codes are presented in (Table3).

Rank	Factor	Frequency
1	Appropriate and fast service in event of damage	14
2	Managing the contact with customer(CRM)	13
3	Providing commitment in over the organization in customer responsiveness	12
4	Customization (product for unique customers)	9

Table 3: Codes of Customer Responsiveness Factors and Frequency

6.4 Creativity Criteria

This factors include 28 frequencies and 2 codes. This means that participants 28 times refer to 4 different codes in this class. The frequencies of codes are presented in (Table4).

Rank	Factor	Frequency
1	The rate of creativity in providing insurance services by insurance agency	15
2	The rate of use of customers as a consultant or coworker by insurance agency	13

Table 4: Codes of Creativity Factors and Frequency

6.5 Internet Services Criteria

This factors include 32 frequencies and 4 codes. This means that participants 32 times refer to 4 different codes in this class. The frequencies of codes are presented in (Table5).

Rank	Factor	Frequency
1	Provide insurance services in electronics	8
2	Provide insurance services by cell phones	6
3	Access to a platform in internet for exchange the experiences of policyholders	5
4	Access to internet for trading policyholders with insurance services and receive free consultation	4

Table 5: Codes of Internet Services Factors and Frequency

6.6 Brand Criteria

This factors include 43 frequencies and 4 codes. This means that participants 43 times refer to 4 different codes in this class. The frequencies of codes are presented in (Table6).

Rank	Factor	Frequency
1	Reliability to insurer	13
2	The popularity of insurance company	12
3	Customer loyalty to insurance company's brand	10
4	Rate of advertising and informing from insurance company	8

Table 6: Codes of Brand Factors and Frequency

7. Result and Discussion

The research participants answers, according to fuzzy numbers scale extracted from the Kahraman (2004 study, are transformed to fuzzy paired comparison matrixes and then by using the group fuzzy AHP formula (equation 1) to a combined matrix (Table7).

Fuzzy triangular number	Theological terms to determine priority
(1,1,1)	Equal importance or priority
($\frac{1}{2}$, 1, $\frac{1}{3}$)	Low importance or priority
($\frac{3}{2}$, 2, $\frac{5}{2}$)	Relatively stronger importance or priority
($\frac{5}{3}$, 3, $\frac{7}{2}$)	Very stronger importance or priority
($\frac{7}{2}$, 4, $\frac{9}{2}$)	Absolute importance or priority

Table 7: Fuzzy Numbers and Theological Terms in AHP Kahraman et.al, 2004)

For all criteria there is one combined matrixes that in total, there were 6 combined matrixes. To obtain the weights of fuzzy factors and their indicators, fuzzy AHP stages are performed on this combined matrixes. The results from ranking and determining the fuzzy weights of this factors are presented in (Tables8-14):

Rank	Indicators	Final ranking
1	Quality	0.2224
2	Customer responsiveness	0.1973
3	Welfare	0.1923
4	Brand	0.1420
5	Internet services	0.1398
6	Creativity	0.1140

Table 8: Final Ranking of Criteria

Rank	Criterion ranking	Final weights
1	Number of dealers	0.2722
2	Dealers availability	0.2639
3	Working hours of insurance dealers	0.2635
4	Rate of flexibility in providing insurance services according to policyholders conditions	0.2004

Table 9: Total Ranking of Welfare Criteria

Rank	Indicators	Final ranking
1	Way of contact of insurance company's staffs	0.2173
2	Rate of presenting free counseling services to policyholders	0.2024
3	Accuracy in doing operation in providing insurance services	0.1801
4	Decor and interior amenities of insurance agency	0.1542
5	Exterior decor and space of insurance agency	0.1319
6	Apparent appearance of staffs in insurance agency	0.1141

Table 10: Total Ranking of Quality Criteria

Rank	Indicators	Final ranking
1	Providing commitment in over the organization in customer responsiveness	0.4374
2	Customization (product for unique customers)	0.2902
3	Appropriate and fast service in event of damage	0.1874
4	Managing the contact with customer(CRM)	0.0850

Table 11: Final Ranking of Customer Responsiveness Criteria

Rank	Indicators	Final ranking
1	Rate of creativity in providing insurance services by insurance agency	0.5405
2	Rate of use of customers as a consultant or coworker by insurance agency	0.4595

Table 12: Final Ranking of Creativity Criteria

Rank	Indicators	Final ranking
1	Provide insurance services in electronics	0.4651
2	Provide insurance services by cell phones	0.2889
3	Access to a platform in internet for exchange the experiences of policyholders	0.1183
4	Access to internet for trading policyholders with insurance services and receive free consultation	0.977

Table 13: Final Ranking for Internet Services Criteria

Rank	Indicators	Final ranking
1	Reliability to insurer	0.3041
2	Popularity of insurance company	0.2584
3	Rate of advertising and informing from insurance company	0.2290
4	Customer loyalty to insurance company's brand	0.2085

Table 14: Final Ranking of Brand Criteria

The results show that quality criteria with 0.2224 weight is in first place and creativity criteria with 0.1420 weight is in final place. Between the welfare criteria, some representatives with 0.2722 fuzzy weight is in first place and after that availability of dealers with

0.2639 weight, working hours of insurance representatives with 0.2635 and the rate of flexibility in providing insurance services according to policyholders with 0.2004 weight are in next places, respectively. Between qualities of services criteria, the way of contact of insurance company's staffs with 0.2173 weight is in first place. The first priority of customer responsiveness is providing commitment in all organization than customer responsiveness with 0.4374 weight, the first priority of creativity criteria is the rate of creativity in presenting insurance services by insurance agencies with 0.5405 weight, the first priority of internet services is providing insurance service in electronic with 0.4951 weight and first priority of brand criteria is assigned to reliability of insurer with 0.3041 weight. Their frequency and codes are shown in below.

7. Conclusion and Suggestions

At first glance it is possible to interpret each identified dimension in study and its structural components. Based on obtained results, insurance industry has a poor performance in some dimensions such as internet services and creativity, however, the factors such as the amounts of discount and free consulting services in dimension of quality of services don't be overlooked. In this study, author want to identify and rank the effective factors on attain competitive advantage of insurance and provide solutions for improve them. In this research, the effective factors on attain competitive advantage were divided to 6 classes. One of the effective factors on attain competitive advantage is internet services criteria.

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